

Mathematical models of electromagnetic influences on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of logistics facilities

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Abstract

The purpose of the work is to conduct an analysis of existing scientific approaches, mathematical models for researching the patterns of electromagnetic influences on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of logistics facilities to determine and justify the most appropriate mathematical model for researching these processes. The article reveals the scientific approaches and views of many scientists regarding the theory and practice of electromagnetic influence on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support and ways to create protection against these influences. The shortcomings of the existing research models of this process are indicated and a number of promising ways to improve them are proposed. The results of the research are one of the stages for substantiating the technical requirements for the creation of protection of cable lines of logistics objects and radio-electronic equipment of weapons and military equipment, in particular technical means of logistical support.

Key words: technical means, weapons and military equipment, logistical support, radio-electronic equipment, cable lines, electromagnetic influence.

Introduction

New means of armed struggle, according to military experts, will be used not so much for conducting military operations as for depriving the enemy of the possibility of active resistance due to damage to its most important objects of the economy and infrastructure, destruction of information and energy space, violation of mental state of the population, etc.

Such weapons include electromagnetic weapons (EMW), which instantly disable cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support and infrastructure, samples of weapons and military equipment of WME and other objects of damage due to the energy of a powerful electromagnetic influence (EMI), which makes it impossible to maintain their serviceable condition at a certain level during the performance of tasks as intended in EMI conditions.

Therefore, in the modern conditions of repelling a large-scale armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, the probability of the enemy using this type of weapon increases significantly, since the facilities and technical means of logistical support are the primary targets for damage by the enemy.

Material and methods.

Theoretical foundations of research

When creating protective devices against the impact of EMI for cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistic support, as well as WME samples, it is necessary to use mathematical models that describe the mechanism of EMI on the equipment elements and

allow to estimate the values of currents and voltages external elements of systems. The interaction of electromagnetic fields with these elements is described by the equations of electrodynamics. It is not possible to obtain a solution in a general form due to the non-stationarity of the parameters of the EMI fields, the length and complex geometry of the interaction between them. Calculation methods based on various simplifications and assumptions are used for approximate estimates of the given currents (Vance E.F., 1982; Bernas S., Tsek Z. 1982). The analysis of literary sources on this problem shows that currently there are not enough universal calculation methods that would allow solving the given task taking into account frequency spectra and all other influencing factors.

The most general solution to the problem of the interaction of electromagnetic fields caused by EMI with the considered objects can be obtained on the basis of the theory of diffraction of electromagnetic waves. However, the solution in such a statement presents significant mathematical difficulties due to the need to take into account the properties of the hidden medium, the geometric shape of the object, and obtain a solution only for estimating currents in the simplest cases: one or two parallel cylinders of infinite length (Balyuk, I.V., 1993). It is practically impossible to use the obtained dependencies for specific calculations.

The solution to the problem of the interaction of EMI fields with cable lines and antenna-feeder devices in general based on Maxwell's equations is obtained only for a straight extension conductor or cable (Mykhailov, M.I. 1979; Messerman D.G., Perelman L.S., 1986).

Formulation of the problem

As a result, it seems appropriate to first provide a solution for this simple case, and then, using methods of mathematical and electrophysical modeling, obtain approximate mathematical models and solutions for specific objects.

The purpose of the article is to conduct an analysis of existing scientific approaches, mathematical models for studies of EMI regularities on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects of logistical support to substantiate the most appropriate mathematical model for the study of these processes.

Research methodology

To realize the goal of the research, we will carry out its decomposition and investigate the following questions:

1) we will analyze the existing mathematical models for studies of the regularities of electromagnetic influences on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects of logistical support to determine and substantiate the most appropriate mathematical model for the study of these processes;

2) substantiation of the mathematical model of the distribution of the electric field during the interaction of the pulsed electromagnetic field with the ionized air environment on the shielded surfaces of the cable lines of the logistics facilities and in the holes of the WME radio-electronic equipment, in particular on the technical means of logistics support.

The methodological tools of the research were Maxwell's level of electrodynamics and the study of the interaction of the pulsed electromagnetic field with the ionized air environment.

Results

The process of interaction EMI of ultra-short-duration (USD) generated by radio-frequency weapons, as one of the types of EMW, with the ionized air environment in the openings of the housing-screens of radio electronic devices is described by the kinetic equation

$$f(v) = \left(\frac{m_e}{2\pi T}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} e^{-\frac{m_e v^2}{2T}}, \quad (1)$$

where T – thermodynamic air temperature;
 m_e – electron mass;
 v – particle flow rate.

In the absence of external EMI in the air environment of the hole ($d \geq 3,8\text{cm}$) the quasi-stationary equilibrium state of the electronic subsystem is established. This is due to the fact that the size of the hole exceeds the length of the free run α - particles in the air environment.

It is known that in the absence of external EMI, the distribution of particles in the hole is Maxwellian, which is described by the well-known expression (Syrotenko, A., 2019):

The distribution function (1) is the starting point for determining the main macroscopic parameters of the ionized air environment. But under the influence of external EMI, the state of its electronic subsystem will change. Depending on the power of EMI, the frequency and duration of the pulse, these processes will differ and in different ways determine the conditions for the protection of cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support.

For the case of large holes and a quasi-equilibrium distribution of particles, or by the equation (expression for the recombination time):

$$\tau_p = \frac{3m_a T_e^{\frac{7}{2}}}{16\sqrt{2\pi e^6} n_i T_n \left(1 + \frac{m_a v^2}{3T_n}\right) n_a \sigma m_e^{\frac{1}{2}}}. \quad (2)$$

For the case of small holes and unbalanced distribution of the electronic component). Equations (1) and (2) must be supplemented with Maxwell's equations connecting the charge density ρ and current i , as well as the voltage of the electric E and magnetic fields B :

$$\begin{cases} \text{rot}\mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c}\mathbf{j} + \frac{1}{c}\frac{\partial\mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \\ \text{rot}\mathbf{E} = -\frac{1}{c}\frac{\partial\mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \text{div}\mathbf{E} = 4\pi\rho \\ \text{div}\mathbf{B} = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

The distribution functions of charged particles found from the solution of kinetic equations (2), (3) make it possible to determine all the macroscopic parameters of the air environment in the holes, gaps, cable channels of the introduction of casings-screens of cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support, or in waveguide antenna inputs of the receiving paths of the equipment, and first of all the dielectric permeability and conductivity of the ionized air medium.

Based on this, in order to determine the impact of EMI on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of facilities and technical means of logistical support, the system of equations (3) should be presented in the following form (Pat. No. 125987 Ukraine):

$$\begin{cases} \nabla\bar{k}\varepsilon_0\mathbf{E}=0; \\ \nabla\mu\mu_0\mathbf{H}=0; \\ \nabla\mathbf{E}=-\mu\mu_0\frac{\partial\mathbf{H}}{\partial t}; \\ \nabla\mathbf{H}=-\bar{k}\varepsilon_0\frac{\partial\mathbf{E}}{\partial t}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{k}$ – vector wave number;
 ε_0, μ_0 – dielectric and magnetic permeability of vacuum;
 μ – relative magnetic permeability.

From the system of equations (4), we obtain the wave equation with respect to the electric field strength E :

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \nabla(\nabla, \mathbf{E}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\bar{k}\mu_0}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2}. \quad (5)$$

A similar equation can be written with respect to the magnetic field strength H :

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = -\frac{\mu\epsilon_0}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{H}}{\partial t^2}. \quad (6)$$

If spatial dispersion is neglected, then expression (5) will have the form:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} = \frac{\bar{k}\mu_0}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2}. \quad (7)$$

Assuming the invariance of the spatial distribution of the electric voltage field during the interaction of pulsed EMI with the ionized air environment of cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support, the three-dimensional problem can be reduced to a two-dimensional one, which makes it possible to switch to a system of cylindrical coordinates.

Then, without taking into account the effect of the magnetic field, equation (7) will be rewritten in the form:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{k}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0.$$

Taking into account (3), the distribution of the electric voltage vector of the EMI pulse of the radio frequency weapon at the air-ionized medium of the hole interface is presented in the form:

$$\mathbf{E}(r=a, \theta \in (-\theta; \theta)) = E_0(t)E_0(\theta) = E_0 \sin(\omega_0 t) \exp\left(-\frac{t-T}{T}\right)^2 \text{Gexp}\left(-\frac{\theta_0^2}{\theta^2}\right), \quad (8)$$

where $\text{Gexp}\left(-\frac{\theta_0^2}{\theta^2}\right)$ – EMI intensity distribution function at the plasma interface;

θ_0 – the maximum angle of irradiation of the ionized air medium of the hole.

The solution of equation (7) taking into account (8) is the following expression:

$$E(r, \theta, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \sum_{i=1}^N e^{j\omega_i t} \sum_{k=1}^M \left(\frac{\cos k\theta}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} E_0(\omega, \theta) \cos k\theta d\theta + \frac{\sin k\theta}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} E_0(\omega, \theta) \sin k\theta d\theta \right) \frac{L_n(r)}{L_n(m)}, \quad (9)$$

where

$$L_n(r) = J_n\left(\frac{r\omega}{c}\right) - \frac{1}{c^2} \left(J_n\left(\frac{r\omega}{c}\right) + \frac{\left(Z_n\left(\frac{a\omega}{c}\right) + Y_n\left(\frac{a\omega}{c}\right) \right)}{N_n\left(\frac{a\omega}{c}\right)} N_n\left(\frac{r\omega}{c}\right) + Z_n\left(\frac{r\omega}{c}\right) \right),$$

where N – the number of harmonics that describe the envelope function of wave packets reflected from the ionized medium;

M – the number of applications of the series describing the function with the required accuracy;

J_n – Bessel function of the first kind in terms of index n ;

N_n – the Neumann function by index n .

Function $E_0(\omega, \theta)$, which stands under the integral in (10), determines the boundary conditions of the problem of determining the distribution of the electric voltage field during the interaction of pulsed EMI with the ionized air medium in the opening of the casing-screen of cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistical support:

$$E_0(\theta, \omega) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^\tau e^{-j\omega t} E \exp\left(-\frac{t^2}{2a^2}\right) \sin \omega t \exp\left(-\frac{\theta_0^2}{\theta^2}\right) dt,_{max} \quad (10)$$

Function $Z_n\left(\frac{r\omega}{c}\right)$ is determined by solving the inhomogeneous Bessel equation for $L_n\left(\frac{r}{c}\right)$ (Lozansky E. D., 1975) which is determined through the plasma frequency parameter, in which the concentration of charged particles, taking into account losses.

Discussion

The scientific novelty of the research results and their practical significance were supported during the discussion between the scientific and pedagogical staff of the Defense Management Center of the National Defense University of Ukraine, including: I. Tkach – Dr of Economics, Professor, Honored Economist of Ukraine; M. Tkach – Dr of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Conclusions

On the basis of existing scientific approaches, mathematical models for studies of EMI regularities on cable lines and radio-electronic equipment of logistics facilities, a mathematical model of the distribution of the field of electric tension during the interaction of a pulsed electromagnetic field with an ionized air environment on the shielded surfaces of cable lines and in the holes of radio-electronic equipment was developed. objects and technical means of logistic support.

The model of the distribution of the field of electric tension during the interaction of a pulsed electromagnetic field with an ionized air environment on the shielded surfaces of cable lines and in the holes of the radio-electronic equipment of objects and technical means of logistic support describes the dynamics of the spatio-temporal distribution of the voltage of the microwave pulse generated by the radio-frequency weapon in the ionized air the environment of the opening of the housing-screen of cable lines and radio-electronic equipment, taking into account kinetic processes in the ionized air environment, in particular, taking into account the effect of the loss of charged particles on the formation of a highly conductive channel in the opening. The peculiarity of the model is that the determination of the voltage distribution of the microwave pulse in the ionized air medium of the hole does not require a numerical solution of the system of Maxwell's equations and is based on the use of parameters found from the solution of the wave equation.

In the future, based on the proposed model, the task is to substantiate the technical requirements for the creation of protection of facilities and technical means of logistical support, as well as WME samples from powerful external EMI based on plasma-like technologies.

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